

Solvent Extraction of Ruthenium(III) from Chloride Solution with Cinnamoylhydroxamic Acid in Isobutyl Alcohol

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THE present paper describes the extraction of ruthenium from aqueous chloride solutions into isobutyl alcohol in the form of its complex with cinnamoylhydroxamic acid (CHA). The extraction photometric procedure is also adopted to evaluate certain extraction parameters.

Experimental

The reagent cinnamoylhydroxamic acid (CHA) was prepared by the literature procedure¹. The reagent was recrystallised and its purity was confirmed by checking its melting point, and by C, H, N analyses. A stock solution of ruthenium(III) was prepared by dissolving ruthenium chloride (1.0 g; 99.9%, Arora Mathey) in 0.1M HCl (100 ml). Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared by mixing 1.0 N acetic acid and 1.0 N NaOH in appropriate volumes².

pH measurements were done with a Systronics 335 digital pH-meter. A Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of absorbances.

Procedure: Distribution equilibria at different pH were studied by shaking the aqueous solution (10 ml; 9.74×10^{-5} M) of ruthenium(III) chloride buffered with acetate solutions and 0.05 M solution of CHA in isobutyl alcohol (10 ml). Two phases were separated after the attainment of the equilibrium. The organic extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and its absorbance was measured at 340 nm against reagent blank. The equilibrium pH of the aqueous phases were measured for each of the solutions. The organic extract gave maximum absorbance at pH 5.9, so the other studies were done at this pH.

In order to study the effect of reagent concentration, the following procedure was adopted. Each 10 ml of aqueous phase buffered at pH 5.9 containing the same amount (9.74×10^{-5} M) of Ru^{III} was shaken with isobutyl alcoholic solution (10 ml) of CHA of varying concentrations. After equilibration, the organic phases were separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbances were measured as stated before.

The effect of chloride ion concentrations was studied over the range 0.005–1.0 M by adding NaCl at a fixed pH 5.9 and fixed reagent concentration 0.01 M. Mole-ratio method was used to determine the metal-ligand ratio and the stability constant of the extractable complex.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data indicate that the ruthenium extraction with CHA is not dependent on chloride ion concentration. The metal:ligand ratio was found to be 1:3 by Job's method as well as by mole-ratio method. This suggested the extraction to occur according to equilibria,

The log *D* vs log [HL]_o plot gave a straight line of slope equal to 2.87, when *D* (distribution ratio for the metal) = [ML_{n(o)}]/[Mⁿ⁺], [HL]_o is the reagent concentration in organic phase, and *K*_{ex} the extraction constant. This value of nearly 3 further confirmed the metal:ligand ratio of 1:3 and also indicated the extracted complex to be a electro-neutral RuL₃ species. The average value of log *K*_{ex} was found to be -10.11 ± 0.09 .

The stepwise formation constants were evaluated by Leden's method as modified by Bag and coworkers³ and were found to be log *K*₁ = 2.20, log *K*₂ = 2.73 and log *K*₃ = 3.60. The increasing trend of the values of *K*₁, *K*₂ and *K*₃ is, however, against the general statistical order. Determination of the factor(s) responsible for such findings requires an extensive QSAR (quantitative structure activity relationship) study, which is presently in progress.

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Bis-4-phthalanilic Acid Sulphone : A New Specific Gravimetric Reagent for Copper(II)

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IN this communication, synthesis of new chelating agent, viz. bis-4-phthalanilic acid sulphone is reported and its potential for microdetection as well as gravimetric estimation of copper in presence

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